

ISic0213

I.Sicily inscription 0213

Language

Latin

Type

funerary

Material

stone

Object

unknown

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

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Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Thermae Himeraeae

Place of origin (modern)

Termini Imerese

Provenance

Lost already when recorded by Gualtherus

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Lost

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. Sex(to) · Raecio □

2. Sex(ti) · I(iberto) · Stephano

3. amici · de · suo

Apparatus

Text of CIL after Gualtherus

Gualtherus: RAECIO · Y

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285252

EDR 127466

EDCS 22100135

Bibliography

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